

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1. Dialysis fluid and culture medium solute concentrations

Solute	DF concentration (mmol/L)	Culture medium Concentration (mmol/L)
Na ⁺	130	121.6
K ⁺	3.00	4.16
Mg ²⁺	0.50	0.71
Ca ²⁺	1.50	1.05
Cl ⁻	110	126.1
CH ₃ COO ⁻	3.00	0
HCO ₃ ⁻	32.0	29.0
Glucose	5.55	17.5

Supplementary Table S2. PBUTs concentrations in healthy individuals, kidney disease patients and as applied within the PBUTs cocktail¹ and in uremic plasma (UP) in this study, with their individual protein binding².

PBUTs	Healthy conc. (μ M) (Mean \pm SD)	Uremic conc. (μ M) (Mean \pm SD)	PBUTs (μ M) ¹	UP (μ M) ²	Protein binding (%) ³	OAT1 affinity (μ M) ⁴
Indoxyl sulfate	2.3 \pm 18.8	173.5 \pm 121.9	100	68.0 \pm 5.8	87-98	20.5
<i>p</i> -cresyl sulfate	10.1 \pm 12.2	122.2 \pm 90.3	500	42.2 \pm 2.5	95	232
<i>p</i> -cresyl glucuronide	0.3 \pm 0.2	30.1 \pm 6.7	40	1.35 \pm 0.10	12-13	-
Indol-3-acetic acid	2.9 \pm 1.7	11.4 \pm 2.3	3	5.28 \pm 0.56	53-69	14.0
Hippuric acid	16.7 \pm 11.2	608.4 \pm 362.8	300	177.2 \pm 11.4	39-41	23.5

Kynurenic acid	0.03 ± 0.01	0.8 ± 0.4	3	2.55 ± 0.20	95	5.1
L-kynurenine	1.9	3.3 ± 0.9	5	4.00 ± 0.42	67	-

¹Concentrations reported on EUTox Uremic Solutes Database (<https://database.uremic-toxins.org> accessed on 28 March 2023) and Mihajlovic et al. [24]. ²Albumin concentration in UP (HSA, 0.70 mM). ³Protein binding values were reported in [28]. ⁴OAT1 affinity constants were reported in [4].